

Beyond Documentation: 3D Technologies for the Interpretation of Renaissance Terracotta Sculpture in Museum Collections

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ABSTRACT

Within the context of the PNRR project CHANGES (Spoke 4), this article explores how 3D imaging technologies can move beyond documentation to function as analytical tools for art-historical research. Focusing on two terracotta works by Antonio Begarelli — *The Lamentation over the Dead Christ* and *The Baptism of Christ* (Gallerie Estensi, Modena)— it investigates how structured-light scanning and photogrammetry can support new forms of interpretative inquiry into Renaissance sculptural practice. Three complementary workflows are tested: monochromy surface simulation, spatial reconstruction, and volumetric comparison. The first highlights how digital reconstruction can reshape the perception of terracotta materiality, while also exposing its dependence on conservation conditions and acquisition constraints. The second demonstrates how virtual environments can be used to reassess compositional arrangements and test hypotheses about fragmented or historically altered configurations, revealing spatial logics not evident in traditional viewing conditions. The third applies mesh-to-mesh comparison and scalar-field analysis to detect subtle morphological correspondences, suggesting potential reuse of workshop models, while treating quantitative outputs as comparative indicators rather than absolute measures. Overall, the study suggests that 3D methods may be particularly effective when used as exploratory and comparative tools rather than as mechanisms for definitive reconstruction. In this capacity, they open new avenues for investigating materiality, spatial composition, and production processes in Renaissance sculpture.

KEYWORDS

digital cultural heritage; photogrammetry; structured light projection scanning; 3D reconstruction; Renaissance sculpture; mesh-to-mesh comparison; 3D simulation

1. Introduction

Three-dimensional technologies have long been employed for the conservation, display and digitisation of Renaissance sculpture. While these applications have significantly improved the preservation and accessibility of sculptural works within museum contexts, their potential as experimental tools for the investigation of production processes, workshop practices, and the stylistic choices of early modern sculptors has yet to be fully developed within art-historical research. Although technologies such as structured light scanning and photogrammetry are now widely used to produce high-resolution meshes for documentation and dissemination, they are still predominantly employed as descriptive instruments rather than as analytical frameworks capable of generating new forms of historical knowledge.

The present study addresses this gap by investigating the new possibilities offered by computational imaging methods for art-historical research through two works by Antonio Begarelli preserved in the Gallerie Estensi in Modena: the *Lamentation over the Dead Christ* and the *Baptism of Christ*, pilot case study developed within the PNRR project CHANGES (Spoke 4: Virtual Technologies for Museums and Art Collections). Terracotta sculpture represents a particularly promising field for digital experimentation; due to its production techniques, it is frequently characterized by complex multi-figure compositions, the extensive use of workshop moulds, and the loss or alteration of original surface treatments. Within this context, they allow for the exploration of digital methodologies for documenting and reconstructing sculptural logics in terms of form, space, and material appearance.

During the acquisition campaigns conducted in 2025, structured-light scanning and photogrammetric techniques have been combined to produce high-resolution digital models of the two works mentioned with the aim of supporting documentation, computational analysis, and simulation within a FAIR-compliant workflow and taxonomy. The resulting datasets are presented here as analytical tools within an experimental framework, to support art-historical research.

More specifically, the article examines the potential of 3D imaging for the simulation of the sculptures' original monochromy. It also explores the reconstruction of spatial relationships among the multiple figures. It moves beyond the mere re-assembly of fragments, since there is scant and only two-dimensional evidence concerning their original disposition, revealing completely new information through the simulation of spatial relationships. Finally, it enables volumetric comparison through quantitative geometry, allowing for the detection of subtle reuses of three-dimensional moulds. By addressing these issues, the study argues that 3D technologies can move beyond documentation and conservation to become a methodological instrument for art-historical analysis.

2. State of the Art

In recent decades, 3D technologies have progressively reshaped approaches to Renaissance sculpture, especially in conservation, museum display, and digital accessibility. Art historians are most familiar with the application of 3D technologies in the field of conservation and reproduction (material or digital) of Renaissance sculptures. Chief among these is the case of *Adam* by Tullio Lombardo (1495–1500, New York, The Metropolitan Museum of Art, inv. 36.163), a fragile marble masterpiece severely fragmented following an accidental fall in 2002 and reassembled by the conservators of the Metropolitan Museum of Art between 2009 and 2014. Using 3D laser scans, the Met conservators created digital models of the fragments and corresponding facsimiles printed in polyurethane foam to simulate the reassembly of the marble pieces both digitally and physically (Riccardelli et al. 2014). Taking a similar approach, but using optical scans and rapid prototyping, between 2011 and 2013 the Opificio delle Pietre Dure (OPD) and UNOCAD srl reassembled Michelangelo's *Saint John the Baptist* (c. 1495), preserved in Úbeda, Spain, which had been dismembered during the Spanish Civil War. Using only black-and-white photographs taken before 1936 as a reference, UNOCAD srl scanned the surviving fragments, digitally reassembled them, and reconstructed the missing parts through digital modelling (Ambrosini, 2014). The OPD then mounted the original fragments together with the reconstructed missing fragments (Lorenzi, Sorella 2014). The reconstruction of the missing elements of Michelangelo's *Saint John the Baptist* has recently been revisited by Factum Foundation (Lowe et al. 2025).

Beyond conservation purposes, museum and exhibition curators employ physical replicas for permanent or temporary display. A 3D-printed replica of the *Censing Angel* (c. 1270) by Arnolfo di Cambio, now in the Harvard University Art Museums (inv. 1957.57.A), has become part of the permanent display of the Museo dell'Opera del Duomo in Florence, alongside the other elements of the medieval façade of Santa Maria del Fiore (Street 2014). In 2023 Gian Lorenzo Bernini's *Saint Sebastian* (private collection) was not loaned for the exhibition *L'immagine sovrana* held in Palazzo Barberini, Rome (Cicconi et al., 2023, p. 166, cat. n. 4). As a result, Factum Foundation scanned the original sculpture, printed a 3D model, moulded it and then cast the final replica in synthetic marble. Finally, 3D scans are now widely conceived as tools to make Renaissance sculptures digitally accessible by creating 3D models that can be fully navigated online. This aspect is particularly relevant for monumental sculptures. Larger-than-life sculptures are rarely entirely freestanding within museum displays and can usually be observed only from floor level. This means that the larger the object, the greater the potential of an enhanced digital experience.

While the above-mentioned practices significantly enhance accessibility and public engagement, they often remain centred on visualisation purposes, with limited integration of analytical or research-oriented functionalities. Therefore, extensive repositories of high-resolution 3D models risk functioning primarily as digital surrogates rather than as instruments capable of generating new information. In fact, 3D technologies open significant new possibilities for art-historical research, particularly through simulation processes, spatial reconstruction, and quantitative geometric analysis. In terms of simulation processes, the digital reconstruction of lost surface layers is particularly significant for Renaissance terracotta sculpture, whose original finishes are often altered by later restorations (mostly dating from the 19th and 20th centuries) imitating bare fired clay. This simulation of uncoated terracotta is historically inconsistent with the original perception of early modern works, which were always conceived to simulate life (with realistic colours) or more prestigious materials such as marble or bronze (with white or black patinas). In this perspective, the simulation of Renaissance monochromy finishes represents a promising, yet still underexplored field compared to the more established digital reconstruction of ancient polychromy (Hemingway et al. 2025). At the same time, monochromy reconstructions generally involve fewer interpretative variables and can rely on surviving comparative examples dating from the 15th and 16th and preserving original surface treatments. Within this framework, 3D simulation contributes not only to visual dissemination, but also to the reconstruction of historically grounded perceptions of sculptural materiality.

The second line of inquiry concerns spatial reconstruction intended as tool to address compositions with interacting multiple figures. Much more frequently than marble, Renaissance terracotta sculptures were made of several figures, either freestanding or anchored to niches or walls. This means that in the domain of terracotta, the potential of digital reconstruction goes far beyond the reconstruction of single fragmented sculptures such as Lombardo's *Adam* or Michelangelo's *Saint John the Baptist*. For example, in 2019, Factum Arte produced a complete scan of Niccolò dell'Arca's celebrated *Lamentation* (c. 1469; Bologna, Santa Maria della Vita), enabling scholars to test various hypotheses regarding the original arrangement of these monumental figures, which are both fragile and difficult to move (Tomassini and Damone 2020), making physical tests too dangerous. The use of digitally reconstructed environments or sculptures therefore enables researchers not only to virtually reassemble fragmented objects, but also to simulate alternative compositional arrangements and evaluate their spatial coherence within broader sculptural contexts.

The third line of inquiry concerns the possibilities to investigate - through digital overlapping and direct comparison of 3D meshes - the production and replication processes of Ancient, Medieval and Renaissance sculptors. Morphological similarity has emerged as a key methodological framework not only for classifying archaeological and cultural heritage artefacts, but also for architectural components, identifying replicas or recurring formal patterns across different historical periods, and supporting historical hypotheses through measurable geometric evidence. Moyano et al. (2022), for instance, compared the geometric profiles of Gothic architectural elements from the Cathedral of Seville and neighbouring churches using algorithmic shape analysis implemented in CloudCompare (<https://www.cloudcompare.org/>), an open-source software for point cloud and mesh processing, followed by statistical evaluation of morphological similarities. Additional studies have applied 3D geometric analysis to archaeological objects to assess shape similarity and production techniques (Zapassky et al. 2006; Koutsoudis and Chamzas 2011; De Reu et al. 2013), while others have developed dedicated computational tools to investigate specific morphological properties, such as the identification of rotational axes in wheel-thrown pottery from different chronological phases (Karasik and Smilansky, 2008). To achieve such precision, the Iterative Closest Point (ICP) algorithm has become a fundamental technique for aligning 3D datasets (Abid et al. 2024; Moyano et

al. 2022; Li et al. 2020). While highly effective, standard ICP can struggle if the models are not roughly aligned beforehand, sometimes getting "stuck" in a slightly wrong position. To overcome this limitation, researchers typically adopt a two-step workflow: an initial coarse alignment followed by ICP refinement, ensuring accurate and reliable comparisons. This approach is widely supported by open-source platforms like CloudCompare which offer integrated tools for these quantitative analyses (Rajendra et al. 2014).

The case study presented in this article focuses on Renaissance terracotta with an innovative approach. Here a premise on the technique and study of Renaissance terracotta is necessary. It is well known that 15th and 16th century sculptors employed moulds to replicate inventions for both market purposes (to sell the same work of art cast in different materials, mostly terracotta or plaster) and creative purposes (to preserve and reuse a three-dimensional artistic invention). The mesh-to-mesh comparison approach has already proven effective for the analysis of fifteenth-century reliefs replicated in several specimens. The replication of entire reliefs was particularly common among Tuscan sculptors, especially for devotional subjects such as the Virgin and Child (see, most recently: Galli et al. 2026). To analyse the subtle topographical variations in plaster casts to uncover production techniques, Gariani et al. (2021) utilized structured light 3D scanning. By performing a precise mesh-to-mesh comparison, they were able to detect millimetric differences in shape and surface topography. This allowed them to identify which casts were produced from the same mould and make solid hypothesis to distinguish original prototypes from later replicas. However, while the replication of whole reliefs is obvious from mere inspection, the identification of reused three-dimensional forms in complex sculptural compositions is much less intuitive to detect, and much more difficult to prove through photographic comparison. This article presents a pioneering use of mesh-to-mesh comparison to demonstrate a specific use of moulds that so far art historians could only hypothesise from mere observation.

3. Methodology

3.1 3D technologies and terracotta sculpture: Antonio Begarelli case studies

The methodological framework developed for this research combines high-resolution 3D acquisition, digital simulation, and quantitative geometric analysis to investigate different aspects of Renaissance terracotta sculpture. Building upon the research perspectives outlined in the State of the Art, the project applies these methodologies to the works of Antonio Begarelli (1499–1565), a celebrated Italian terracotta master working mostly in Emilia Romagna. The two works by Begarelli selected as case study are both preserved at the Gallerie Estensi in Modena. Begarelli made the *Baptism* (inv. no. 4259) and the *Lamentation* (inv. no. 4260) for the church of San Salvatore in Modena. No archival document related to this commission has emerged so far. However, it is most likely that Begarelli made these sculptures after 1534, when San Salvatore was completely rebuilt after a fire (Bonsanti 1992, pp. 171-176; Ravaglia 2024, pp. 136-139, 368-380).

While the *Lamentation* is still preserved as a complete high relief (Fig. 1), the *Baptism* has come down to us in several fragments. An engraving by Giuseppe Guizzardi dated 1823 is the oldest visual source showing the display of the *Baptism* (Fig. 2). *Christ* and *Saint John the Baptist* stood within a niche decorated by a canopy (now lost), while the circular bas-relief representing the *Dove of the Holy Spirit* was attached to the rear wall of the recess above the two main figures; four additional *Seraphs* were placed around the *Dove*. It is unclear how and when the *Lamentation* and the *Baptism* left San Salvatore, but it is certain that by 1894 the sculptures were already in the Gallerie Estensi (*Le Gallerie Nazionali Italiane*, 1893, p. 50). A photograph by Orlandini dating from the beginning of the XX century shows the *Baptism* reassembled in the galleries, where a niche was built to recreate a display similar – but not identical – to the 1823 engraving. During this reconstruction, the four *Seraphs* were moulded and replicated in plaster to surround the *Dove* with a full circle of winged heads. This display was completely arbitrary and significantly distorted the original composition attested by the 1823 engraving. Finally, during the 1970's the niche was dismantled and since then the *Dove* and the *Seraphs* have not been on display (they are currently preserved in the museum's storage at Palazzo Coccapani in Modena), while *Christ* and *Saint John the Baptist* are now placed on a high pedestal without any background (Mezzetti 1976).

Fig. 1: the *Lamentation* by Antonio Begarelli

Fig. 2: Engraving by Giuseppe Guizzardi (1823)

The methodological framework was defined in response to the specific material, spatial, and conservation characteristics of the selected sculptures and required the integration of complementary digital workflows addressing distinct but interconnected research questions. This required a high-resolution digital acquisition workflow capable of supporting both qualitative visual analysis and quantitative geometric investigation, with particular attention to the geometric accuracy and methodological transparency of the resulting 3D datasets (Barzaghi et al. 2024; Barzaghi et al. 2025). The entire digitisation pipeline followed an established procedure (Bordignon et al. 2024). The acquisition phase involved the combined use of structured light scanning and photogrammetry.

The aim was not only to document the sculptures, but also to produce multiple versions of each 3D model adapted to different analytical and dissemination purposes (Barzaghi et al. 2025a): the **RAW** data, namely the datasets obtained directly from the acquisition campaign; the **RAWp**, i.e. the incomplete model with possible missing portions, generated exclusively from the acquired data and therefore more strongly affected by acquisition methods and spatial constraints;

the **DCHO**, the complete model integrated through manual and semi-automatic procedures; and finally the **DCHOo**, the optimised model designed to be efficient and suitable for publication in real-time web-based interactive environments. All statues were digitised through the combined use of the Artec Leo scanner and the Artec Space Spider (formerly Artec II) (Fig. 3). The former was employed to capture the overall geometry, achieving up to 0.1 mm 3D point accuracy; the latter, with a resolution of up to 0.05 mm, was used to refine occluded and hard-to-reach areas that were less accessible to the first device, thus completing the mesh and ensuring maximum resolution and geometric accuracy. For morphological analyses, the scanner-derived data proved to be appropriate and effective.

In addition, a dedicated photographic set was acquired for each object using a Sony ILCE-6100 camera equipped with a Sony E 35mm F1.8 OSS lens. These images played a crucial role in generating high-quality textures, ensuring a high degree of photorealism and enabling further investigation of color and material composition. To allow comprehensive acquisition, the artworks were moved from their museum setting whenever possible. In the case of the *Baptism*, the statues were temporarily relocated to allow a complete 360-degree survey of both figures. For the *Lamentation*, however, relocation was not feasible. The scanning and photogrammetric survey was therefore conducted in all accessible areas, except for the rear side placed directly against the wall, with recessed sections manually integrated in Artec Studio.

Fig. 3: *Christ and Saint John the Baptist* (left) and *Lamentation* (right) acquisition using Artec Space Spider

3.2 Research workflows

The research was therefore structured around three principal workflows according to the specific analytical problem. The first concerns the digital simulation of original monochrome surfaces to reconstruct historically grounded perceptions of sculptural appearance and materiality. The second focuses on the virtual reconstruction and spatial simulation of fragmented sculptural installations, with particular attention to the relationship between sculptural components and architectural settings. Finally, the third approach employs high-resolution 3D acquisition and quantitative mesh comparison techniques to investigate processes of replication, reuse, and modification within workshop practices.

3.2.1 White monochromatic surface simulation

Although the *Lamentation* and *Baptism* are covered by a reddish varnish applied during nineteenth- and twentieth-century restorations to imitate the colour of fired clay, historical evidence demonstrate that these sculptures originally featured a white surface coating and a subtly reflective surface intended to simulate marble. Their current appearance therefore does not correspond to their original visual conception.

However, a substantial number of surviving works by Antonio Begarelli preserve their original surface treatment such as the sculptures in the churches of San Benedetto in Polirone near Mantua and San Giovanni Evangelista in Parma, or the *Crucifixion* group (Fig. 4) in the Staatliche Museen zu Berlin (Skulpturensammlung und Museum für Byzantinische Kunst, inv. No. 315) These examples provide valuable comparative evidence for the material and chromatic characteristics of Begarelli's sculptures.

Fig. 4. Begarelli's sculptures preserving the original surface treatment (the Staatliche Museen zu Berlin).

As mentioned above, the selected case studies, currently preserved at the Gallerie Estensi, have lost this original surface treatment. The three-dimensional models of the sculptures proved instrumental in enabling further texture modifications aimed at simulating their original appearance through scenarios that, while necessarily hypothetical, were informed by comparative material evidence.

To simulate the sculptures' original white appearance, two different approaches were tested. The first involved the application of a seamless physically based rendering texture (PBR) reproducing the material characteristics of white terracotta. However, when applied to the models, this solution resulted a substantial loss of surface detail, with a significant flattening of both the fine morphological features and the chromatic variations preserved in the acquired albedo textures (i.e. the original colour information captured from the object's surface). Consequently, this approach failed to preserve the visual complexity required for interpretative purposes. The second approach relied on the post-processing of the original texture maps using Adobe Photoshop (<https://www.adobe.com/products/photoshop.html>). Adjustments to saturation, contrast, and tonal distribution were carried out to approximate a neutral white appearance while retaining surface irregularities and material nuances (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5: Original texture of the *Christ* (left) and white simulation (right)

A uniform processing workflow was not applied across all sculptures due to variations in surface conditions, conservation histories, and acquisition environments. Differences between lighting condition and general settings at Palazzo Coccapani and the Gallerie Estensi produced residual chromatic inconsistencies despite the application of a standardised white balance correction workflow. Additionally, the *Lamentation* exhibits a markedly more consistent surface and fabric compared to the other sculptures, further preventing the application of a single homogenising texture treatment.

Once the texture maps had been finalised in Adobe Photoshop, they were applied to the corresponding 3D models. A roughness value of 0.450 was then assigned to the material in order to approximate, on the basis of comparisons with extant examples, the slightly reflective quality of the original, white-coated terracotta surface, while preventing an overly glossy effect that would be inconsistent with the material evidence (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6: 3D rendering of the white monochromy simulation of *Lamentation* (left) and *Baptism* (right)

3.2.2 The *Baptism*'s spatial reconstruction

Originally mounted within a niche and now preserved only in a fragmentary state, the *Baptism* consists of two principal figures – *Christ* and *Saint John* – and several secondary terracotta elements, including the *Dove of the Holy Spirit* and four Seraphs. While the two main figures are currently displayed at the Gallerie Estensi adjacent to the *Lamentation*, the additional elements are preserved in the museum storage at Palazzo Coccapani in Modena. The original arrangement of the ensemble is documented only in a nineteenth-century engraving (Guizzardi and Tomba, 1823), which constitutes the primary visual source for reconstructing the *Baptism* presumed original configuration (Fig. 7). Since the sculptures are currently divided between different locations, the acquisition campaign was conducted in two phases using consistent digitisation methodologies and acquisition parameters.

Within this context, the digital model enabled a virtual recomposition of the group, facilitating the study of the spatial relationships between sculptural elements and their architectural support. This aspect proved particularly significant because the reliefs were not conceived as freestanding figures, but as components structurally anchored to a curved niche surface. The reconstruction process therefore enabled the evaluation of volumetric relationships, orientation, and spatial coherence within the original installation; while simultaneously reducing the speculative component typically associated with hypothetical reconstructions of fragmented sculptural environments (see Tommasini and Damone 2020). Therefore, the aim of the digital reconstruction is contributing to the visualisation of a more coherent compositional arrangement of the group, which is currently presented to the public in a fragmentary and potentially misleading manner (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7: Current display of *Christ* and *Saint John* at Gallerie Estensi (left) and digital reconstruction's 3D rendering of the *Baptism* based on historical sources (right)

The reconstruction process faced significant limitations due to the scarcity and heterogeneity of available sources. Therefore, the repositioning of the figures necessarily relied on a two-dimensional visual source, and the reconstruction was conceived primarily as a visual and interpretative tool. For the visualisation the DCHOO version of each model were imported into the 3D modelling and rendering software Blender (<https://www.blender.org/>) at a 1:1 scale. The incision was likewise imported as a texture mapped onto a planar mesh and used as a spatial reference for the placement of the figures.

The main methodological challenge concerned the definition of depth relationships within the ensemble. To address this issue, the figures of the *Dove of the Holy Spirit* and the *Seraphs* were positioned on the same z -axis. The *Dove of the Holy Spirit* was slightly rotated along the y-axis and inclined downward, in accordance with the engraving. The *Seraphs*, were arranged symmetrically on either side of the composition, following the layout suggested by the engraving (Fig. 8).

An additional element supporting the reconstruction of the original composition of the *Baptism* is the hypothesis that the group was conceived as a pendant to the *Lamentation*. This interpretation is further reinforced by the comparable canopy documented in the historical engraving, which suggests a compositional correspondence between the two sculptural groups. the three-dimensional model of the *Lamentation* was introduced into the virtual environment and employed as a reference for establishing the overall height and vertical articulation of the *Baptism* ensemble. The use of this comparative model contributed to constraining the reconstruction within plausible spatial parameters consistent with the presumed original display context (Fig. 9).

Fig. 8: Lateral perspectives of the *Baptism* components for depth relationships analysis

Fig. 9: Digital simulation of the *Baptism* as a pendant to the *Lamentation* based on compositional correspondences

3.2.3 The *Lamentation*: a mesh-to-mesh comparison for art-historical analysis

The third research workflow in Begarelli’s case study builds on volumetric analysis to investigate a different artistic practice. While mesh-to-mesh comparison has been successfully applied to replicated devotional reliefs (Gariani et al. 2021; Galli et al. 2026), this study extends it to individual sculptural components reused with local modifications across different figures by the same artist. Historical sources and surviving visual evidence attest that terracotta sculptors commonly took plaster casts from their completed sculptures to reuse individual specific elements – such as heads, hands, or legs– multiple times with slight modifications (Calogero 2024, p. 151 and p. 288). In these processes, clay was pressed into a plaster mould and then reworked while still pliable, allowing artists to alter orientation, proportions, or surface details according to compositional needs. Methodologically, this adaptive reuse is more complex than full relief replication, as local modifications partially obscure geometric correspondence between reused elements. Within this framework, high-resolution 3D acquisition and quantitative mesh comparison were used to detect subtle morphological similarities between selected sculptural elements in the *Lamentation* group, particularly the heads of the three angels. The workflow was designed to identify shared geometric structures that are not easily observable through conventional visual analysis, while also accounting for local variations introduced during manual reworking.

The RAWp version of the *Lamentation*’s 3D model was selected as the primary reference for comparison, as it exhibits the highest geometric resolution and remains entirely free from data manipulation (i.e., no automatic or semi-automatic gap filling was performed by the processing software). This choice was motivated by the need to compare the heads of the three angels present in the overall sculpture in support of the art-historical analysis, using the most faithful geometric representation available (Fig. 10). All comparison and analytical procedures were carried out in CloudCompare. In the following sections, the workflow stages carried out to obtain the quantitative analysis results are presented.

Fig. 10: Selection of the angels’ heads from the global sculpture and starting point orientation before alignment

The analysis was carried out by comparing the angels’ heads in pairs. In this process, one mesh acted as the reference, while the other was registered onto it. Because mesh-to-mesh distance computation in CloudCompare is inherently directional, the reference mesh was systematically selected according to geometric completeness and acquisition quality to minimise artefacts related to missing data, local occlusions, or uneven point distribution (Table 1). Given that all meshes originated from the same acquisition campaign, shared the same metric scale, and were processed through an identical workflow, this approach was considered methodologically consistent for comparative analysis.

Angel head	Mesh resolution (triangles)
Central angel (A)	206,810
Right angel (B)	165,671
Left angel (C)	136,739

Table 1. Angels’ head mesh resolution

An initial alignment was performed using the *Align (Point Pairs Picking)* tool, which allows the manual selection of corresponding anatomical landmarks (e.g., tip of the nose, chin, ear) on the two meshes. This step provides a coarse alignment in cases of significant initial misalignment or scale differences and serves as a preparatory phase for the subsequent fine registration. Fine registration was then achieved using the *Iterative Closest Point (ICP)* algorithm, which automatically refines the alignment by minimizing point-to-point distances between the two meshes. This method is particularly suitable when the models share the same scale and originate from the same acquisition context, as in the present case.

To compute the geometric discrepancies between the two meshes, a maximum distance threshold was defined (± 2 mm) to generate a scalar field representing mesh-to-mesh distances (Fig. 11). The resulting scalar fields were visualised using a color-coded scale, where blue indicates minimal distances (near-zero deviation) and near-perfect correspondence between surfaces; green represents small but detectable differences; yellow corresponds to moderate geometric variations; and red highlights areas of maximum distance, indicating significant deformation, misalignment, or loss of correspondence between the compared models. The colour gradient follows a numerical scale that can be inspected through the scalar field display parameters.

Fig. 11: Alignment phase (left) and ICP fine registration with scalar field (right) between angel A and angel B

Three quantitative metrics were considered for data analysis:

- **ICP RMS (mm)** – Registration accuracy: measures the root mean square error of the ICP alignment; lower values indicate better surface overlap.
- **Mean Distance (mm)** – Average deviation: represents the mean distance between the surfaces of the two meshes; lower values correspond to higher similarity.
- **Standard Deviation of Distance (mm)** – Local variation: quantifies the variability of distances across the surface; lower values suggest a more homogeneous distribution of differences, without local anomalies.

The ± 2 mm threshold was selected in relation to both the metric resolution of the acquired meshes and the scale of the analysed sculptural features, allowing the exclusion of insignificant micro-variations while preserving morphologically meaningful discrepancies.

As summarised in Table 2 and Fig. 12, the quantitative analysis suggests a clear hierarchy of morphological similarity among the three angels. The comparison between the central angel (A) and the right angel (B) exhibits the highest degree of correspondence, as indicated by the lowest mean distance (0.35 mm) and the lowest ICP RMS value (1.67 mm), reflecting both a robust registration and minimal surface deviation. This pair represents the most compact comparison

suggesting a particularly close morphological correspondence potentially compatible with shared production procedures or the reuse of related sculptural models.

The comparison between the central angel (A) and the left angel (C) yields intermediate results, with a mean distance of 0.74 mm and a slightly higher RMS value. Although overall morphological coherence is preserved, the increase in average deviation points to more evident variations, potentially related to differences in facial proportions, expression, or modelling approach.

The comparison between the right angel (B) and the left angel (C) shows the lowest degree of similarity, with the highest mean distance (1.07 mm) and the highest RMS value (2.51 mm). Despite successful alignment, these values indicate more pronounced morphological differences, suggesting a greater stylistic distance that may be relevant for interpreting variations within the sculptural group.

Comparison	Reference	Registered model	ICP Final RMS (mm)	Mean Distance (mm)	Std Dev (mm)	ICP points	Max distance (mm)
1	Central angel (A)	Right angel (B)	1.67	0.35	1.37	45,231	2.0
2	Central angel (A)	Left angel (C)	2.05	0.74	1.36	44,827	2.0
3	Right angel (B)	Left angel (C)	2.51	1.07	1.17	44,677	2.0

Table 2. Quantitative summary of the comparisons between the angels' heads

Fig. 12: Mesh-to-mesh comparison results

To enable a uniform comparison across different metrics, all distance-based results were converted into a unified similarity scale using inverse normalisation. Each metric was mapped onto a 0–1 range, where 1 corresponds to the optimal condition (minimum error) and 0 to the least favourable one (maximum error). This transformation assigns higher similarity scores to lower geometric deviations, enabling a coherent interpretation across indicators. Standard inverse normalisation formulas were applied, allowing quantitative results to be converted into a comparable similarity index:

$$\text{Similarity}_{\text{norm}} = 1 - \frac{x - \min}{\max - \min}$$

The three quantitative indicators (ICP RMS, Mean Distance, and Standard Deviation of distances) were treated with equal weight and combined into a single similarity index by computing the arithmetic mean of their normalised values (Table 4). This composite index provides a synthetic yet interpretable measure of geometric similarity between mesh pairs. The final similarity index should therefore be interpreted as a comparative heuristic tool intended to facilitate the relative ranking of morphological affinity among the analysed mesh pairs, rather than as an absolute metric of sculptural correspondence. Based on these premises, the resulting scores reveal a ranking among the comparisons, with the highest similarity observed between A and B, followed by A and C, and finally B and C (Fig. 13).

Comparison	ICP RMS (norm.)	Mean Distance (norm.)	Std Dev (norm.)	Final similarity (%)
A vs B	0.789	1.000	0.000	59.6
A vs C	1.000	0.514	0.050	52.1
B vs C	0.000	0.000	1.000	33.3

Table 4. Normalised similarity scores and final similarity index

Fig. 13: Similarity percentage across angels' comparisons after standard inverse normalisation

4. Discussion and conclusion

This article has explored how 3D technologies can support the analysis of Renaissance terracotta sculpture through three complementary lines of inquiry: monochromy surface simulation, spatial reconstruction, and volumetric comparison. Rather than proposing isolated technical experiments, these workflows were designed to address specific interpretative problems related to sculptural perception, original display, and workshop practices.

Overall, the results show that digital tools can move beyond documentation and become instruments for art-historical research. The monochromy simulation of Begarelli's sculptures suggests how surface reconstruction can reframe modern perceptions of terracotta as a material, although the texture outcome remains dependent on heterogeneous conservation conditions, acquisition constraints, and local surface heterogeneity. The spatial reconstruction of the *Baptism* demonstrates how virtual environments can be used to test compositional hypotheses and explore lost contexts, while necessarily retaining a degree of interpretative uncertainty in case of fragmentary visual sources. At the same time, the possibility of interacting with the model from non-front-facing viewpoints proved crucial for reassessing the spatial logic of the ensemble: lateral and oblique views clarified the original alignment and interdependence of the sculptural components, revealing a more coherent arrangement than that suggested by the physical recomposition dismantled in the 1970s. This evidence also opens perspectives for future reconfigurations of the group within the museum, informed by digitally tested spatial configurations.

The mesh-to-mesh comparison confirms the potential of quantitative geometry for detecting subtle correspondences linked to reuse and replication practices. The integration of structured-light scanning, ICP registration, and scalar-field visualisation enabled the identification of subtle morphological correspondences not fully detectable through visual analysis alone. In particular, the initial alignment of the three angel heads, once isolated and oriented within a shared reference system, produced an immediate visual correspondence in their volumetric structures. This apparent volumetric correspondence was further confirmed by the computational analysis, as synthesized by the similarity index, which yielded varying percentage values across the compared models. The results suggest the reuse of a common underlying model subsequently modified during the modelling process, while clay was still pliable. At the same time, the approach remains sensitive to directional computation choices and limited dataset size, meaning that the resulting similarity index should be read as a comparative heuristic tool rather than as an absolute measure of sculptural correspondence.

Taken together, these workflows suggest that 3D methods are equally significant when used as exploratory and comparative tools rather than as mechanisms for definitive reconstruction. At the same time, their application demonstrates how digital approaches can actively generate new forms of art-historical inquiry, particularly when used to interrogate material, spatial, and production-related aspects of Renaissance sculpture that are otherwise difficult to access through traditional methodologies.

To strengthen such interpretative frameworks, future developments may involve the expansion of comparative datasets, the implementation of more controlled acquisition and colour-calibration protocols according to the environment constraints, and the integration of material reflectance analyses. More broadly, the methodologies presented here point towards a growing potential for 3D-based research to contribute not only to documentation and reconstruction, but also to hypothesis-building within the study of early modern sculpture.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

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Luisa Ammirati: Methodology, Writing – review & editing

Alice Bordignon: Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing

Marcello Calogero: Conceptualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing

Francesca Fabbri: Methodology, Investigation, Writing – original draft

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this manuscript, the authors used a large language model (LLM)-based tool to support language editing and paraphrasing for clarity and readability, and to assist in the formulation of a provisional paper title.

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